

An efficient synthesis, characterization and biological activity of novel Schiff bases of 2-aryl-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide derivatives

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Abstract : A series of *N'*-arylidene-2-aryl-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (Schiff bases) 3a₁-3d₄ were synthesized by condensation reaction of 2-aryl-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (2a-2d) with substituted aromatic aldehyde. The characterization of all these novel synthesized compounds 3a₁-3d₄ were established on the basis of spectral studies (IR, NMR and Mass) and elemental analysis. The anti-microbial activities of these compounds were tested *in vitro* by agar diffusion cup-plate method against two Gram-negative *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and two Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* bacteria and fungi *Candida albicans* at 100 µg/ml concentrations. All these compounds have displayed significant or moderate activities against the test microorganisms.

Keywords : Schiff bases, benzimidazole, carbohydrazide, biological activity.

Introduction

Heterocyclic compounds are very frequently used in the synthesis of novel drugs with new mechanisms of action. In recent years, the favorable therapeutic properties of imidazole or benzimidazole related drugs agents such as Rabeprazole, Pantoprazole (antiulcer); Candesartan, Valsartan (antihypertensive); Albendazole, Mebendazole and Thiabendazole (anthelmintic) drugs have prompted medicinal chemists to synthesize numerous novel therapeutic agents. The literature survey shows a large numbers of benzimidazole derivatives have been found to exhibit various therapeutic properties such as antibacterial^{1,2}, antifungal³, antiviral⁴, antihypertensive⁵, antiproliferative⁶, anticancer⁷, antioxidant⁸, antidiabetic⁹, antiallergic¹⁰, antitumor¹¹, anti-HIV¹² and antiprotozoal¹³. In the same way Schiff bases are the significant class of compounds that has gained much importance in recent year due to their potential applications in biological, clinical, analytical and industrial aspect. The first synthesis of Schiff base was reported in the 19th century by H. Schiff in 1864¹⁴.

Schiff's base also known as imines, azomethine and anils. The literature survey shown that the presence of loan pair of electron in sp² hybridized orbital of nitrogen atom of the azomethine group has considerable chemical and biological importance. Schiff's bases have also been shown to exhibit a broad range of biological activities including antibacterial^{15,16}, antiviral¹⁶, antifungal¹⁶, antimalarial¹⁷, anti-inflammatory¹⁸, anticancer¹⁹, antitubercular²⁰, antiproliferative²¹, antioxidant²¹, antitumor²², anti-HIV²³, antidibitic²⁴ and antiplatelet²⁵. Owing to the immense biological importance of Schiff bases and benzimidazole derivatives, we now synthesized a novel series of benzimidazole fused Schiff bases derivatives and investigated their potential biological activity against different microbes.

Results and discussion

In the present work methyl 2-aryl-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole-4-carboxylate (**1a-1d**) were synthesized by the condensation reaction of methyl-2,3-diaminobenzoate with aromatic aldehyde in the presence

ammonium chloride in ethanol. Later compounds **1a-1d** was treated with hydrazine hydrate to produced 2-aryl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**2a-2d**). These hydrazide compounds were condensed with substituted aromatic aldehyde in the presence of few drops of acetic acid as a catalytic amount in absolute ethanol to produce a series of Schiff bases (**3a₁-3d₄**). The synthesis route is outline in Scheme 1.

The chemical structure of the synthesized Schiff base (**3a₁-3d₄**) were characterization by FT-IR, ¹H NMR, MS and elements analysis. The FT-IR spectra of the Schiff bases (**3a₁-3d₄**) showed absorption band at 3116–3442 cm⁻¹ due to N-H str. vibration, band at 1656–1672 cm⁻¹ due to C=O str. vibration and band at 1578–1591 cm⁻¹ due to azomethine group C=N str. vibration. The nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) of Schiff bases (**3a₁-3d₄**) showed singlet at δ 8.38–8.53 indicating presence of azomethine (N=CH-) proton, a sharp singlet appear at δ 12.88–13.10 indicating presence of -CONH- proton and at δ 13.36–13.60 is indicating presence of imidazole singlet proton. In the mass spectrum, Schiff bases

(**3a₁-3d₄**) showed a peak at *m/z*, which matches its sodium salt molecular formula. The spectral data lend strong support to the proposed structures of all these novel synthesized compounds. Physicochemical data, elemental analysis results and spectral data of all these compounds are given in Experimental section.

Antibacterial activity :

The antibacterial and antifungal activities of the newly synthesized compounds (**3a₁-3d₄**) were evaluated by agar cup-plate diffusion method²⁶ by measuring the zone of inhibition in mm. These novel synthesized compounds screened against Gram-negative *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* bacteria and fungi *Candida albicans*. All the samples and standards were prepared by dissolving in dimethylformamide (DMF) to get a concentration of 100 µg. The standards (Ciprofloxacin and Fluconazole) were used as positive control and 100 µL of DMF was used as negative control, zone of inhibition were recorded in mm. The results of antimicrobial screening of all the newly synthesized com-

Scheme 1. Synthesis routes for benzimidazole derive Schiff bases (**3a₁-3d₄**).

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of the novel synthesized compounds

Compds.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) in DMF	Zone of inhibition in mm					Antifungal activity <i>C. albicans</i>
		Antibacterial activity					
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>M. luteus</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	
3a₁	100	17	19	17	19	16	19
3a₂	100	21	20	22	19	19	20
3a₃	100	25	21	26	24	24	23
3a₄	100	19	18	20	18	18	19
3b₁	100	20	19	21	20	20	24
3b₂	100	21	20	19	22	22	22
3b₃	100	26	23	26	25	25	24
3b₄	100	22	20	21	19	19	24
3c₁	100	24	22	25	26	26	24
3c₂	100	25	22	26	25	25	25
3c₃	100	28	24	28	26	26	29
3c₄	100	24	21	24	21	21	23
3d₁	100	21	20	23	20	20	24
3d₂	100	22	23	23	21	21	20
3d₃	100	26	24	26	24	24	25
3d₄	100	22	20	26	24	24	25
Ciprofloxacin	100	30	28	27	29	29	–
Fluconazole	100	–	–	–	–	–	28

pounds are presented in Table 1. Most of synthesized compounds showed significant to moderate antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

All chemicals and solvents were used of AR grade. The melting points of all the synthesized compounds were determined in one end open capillary tubes on a Buchi melting point apparatus. IR spectra were recorded on Bruker FT-IR spectrometer using KBr pellets in the range 4000–600 cm^{-1} . Nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR) spectra were recorded on Bruker 400 NMR spectrometer. Chemical shifts are reported in parts per million (ppm) using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard. Mass spectra recorded a Waters mass spectrometer. IR, ^1H NMR and MS were consistent with assigned structure. Element analyses (CHN) were undertaken with Perkin-Elmer model 240C analyzer. The completion of reaction and purity of compounds were checked on thin layer chromatography (TLC) on silica gel-G

(Merck) coated aluminum plates, visualized by ultra violet light 254 nm. Developing solvents were chloroform : methanol : liq. ammonia (17 : 3 : 0.5).

Procedure for the preparation of methyl 2-aryl-1H benzo[d]imidazole-4-carboxylate (1a-1d) :

To a mixture of methyl-2,3-diamino benzoate (5 g, 30 mmol) and equal mole of correspond aldehydes in 50 ml of ethanol was added NH_4Cl (7.5 g, 140 mmol). The resulting mixture was refluxed for 2–3 h. The completion of the reaction was confirmed by TLC (ethyl acetate : hexane, 1 : 2). The reaction mass were poured into ice water and product was filtered. The product was purified by recrystallization from ethanol to give pure product. The same procedure was used for all other compounds. Yield : 70–80%.

Methyl 2-phenyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-4-carboxylate (1a) :

IR (KBr) : 3382.34 (N-H str.), 2878.28, 2794.35 (C-H str.), 1718.64 (C=O str.); ^1H NMR (400 MHz,

DMSO- d_6) : δ 3.92 (3H, s, -COOCH₃), 7.35–8.26 (8H, m, Ar), 13.48 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). Anal. Found : C, 71.36; H, 4.75; N, 11.07. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₂N₂O₂ : C, 71.42; H, 4.79; N, 11.10.

Procedure for the preparation of 2-phenyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (2a-2d) :

To a mixture of methyl 2-aryl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-4-carboxylate (**1a-1d**) (20 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (60 mmol) were refluxed in 25 ml isopropylalcohol. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 4–5 h. The completion of reaction was confirmed by TLC (n-hexane : ethyl acetate, 2 : 1). The reaction mixtures cool to ambient temperature. The product was filtered and washed with isopropyl alcohol. Yield : 80–85%.

2-Phenyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (2a) :

IR (KBr) : 3426.29, 3231.26 (N-H, N-H₂ str.), 3051.34 (aromatic C-H), 2929.34, 2846.19 (C-H), 1672.52 (C=O str.), 1256.43 (C-N str.); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 4.67 (2H, s, -NH₂), 7.40–8.29 (8H, m, Ar), 12.85 (1H, s, -NH), 13.52 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). Anal. Found : C, 66.61; H, 4.74; N, 22.18. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₂N₄O : C, 66.65; H, 4.79; N, 22.21.

General procedure for the preparation of Schiff bases (hydrazones) (3a₁-3d₄) :

To a mixture of equal mole of 2-phenyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**2a-2d**) and substituted aldehydes were refluxed in 10 ml absolute ethanol for 5–8 h. After completion of reaction (TLC), the reaction mixture cool to ambient temperature and the solid obtained was collected by filtration and recrystallisation in a mixture of ethanol and DMF (8 : 2).

N'-Benzylidene-2-phenyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (3a₁) :

IR (KBr) : 3421.03, 3141.12 (N-H Str.), 3037.43 (aromatic C-H str.), 2964.64, 2891.81 (C-H str.), 1664.45 (C=O str.), 1585.81 (C=N str.), 1252.14 (C-N str.); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 7.12–8.29 (13H, m, Ar), 8.42 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 12.96 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.56 (1H, s, -NH

imidazole). MS : m/z 363.21 (M+Na), m.p. 260–262°C. Anal. Found : C, 74.05; H, 4.70; N, 16.39. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₆N₄O : C, 74.10; H, 4.74; N, 16.46.

N'-(4-Methoxybenzylidene)-2-phenyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (3a₂) :

IR (KBr) : 3415.31, 3120.42 (N-H str.), 3055.778 (aromatic C-H str.), 2981.54, 2868.48 (C-H str.), 1667.82 (C=O str.), 1581.71 (C=N str.), 1250.24 (C-N str.); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 3.80 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 7.08–8.28 (12H, m, Ar), 8.49 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 12.93 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.52 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 393.22 (M+Na), m.p. 295–297°C. Anal. Found : C, 70.25; H, 4.86; N, 15.07. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₈N₄O₂ : C, 71.34; H, 4.90; N, 15.13.

N'-(4-Nitrobenzylidene)-2-phenyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (3a₃) :

IR (KBr) : 3422.26, 3148.54 (N-H str.), 3051.44 (aromatic C-H str.), 2957.64, 2885.26 (C-H str.), 1658.48 (C=O str.), 1578.98 (C=N str.), 1240.25 (C-N str.); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 7.42–8.32 (12H, m, Ar), 8.52 (1H, s =CH azomethine), 13.10 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.59 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 409.05 (M+Na), m.p. 308–310°C. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₅N₅O₃ : C, 65.41; H, 3.87; N, 18.11. Anal. Found : C, 65.45; H, 3.92; N, 18.17.

2-Phenyl-N'-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (3a₄) :

IR (KBr) : 3412.42, 3120.24 (N-H str.), 3024.40 (aromatic C-H str.), 2924.40, 2842.50 (C-H str.), 1656.60 (C=O str.), 1589.12 (C=N str.), 1238.27 (C-N str.); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 7.18–8.16 (11H, m, Ar), 8.44 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 12.94 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.48 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 369.19 (M+Na), m.p. 248–250°C. Anal. Found : C, 65.83; H, 4.01; N, 16.12. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₄N₄OS : C, 65.88; H, 4.07; N, 16.17.

N'-Benzylidene-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (3b₁) :

IR (KBr) : 3442.03, 3128.54 (N-H str.), 3046.59 (aromatic C-H str.), 2982.24, 2828.28 (C-H str.),

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1660.24 (C=O str.), 1591.27 (C=N str.), 1242.14 (C-N str.); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 3.76 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 7.10–7.96 (12H, m, Ar), 8.41 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 13.07 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.53 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 393.19 (M+Na), m.p. 275–276°C. Anal. Found : C, 71.28; H, 4.86; N, 15.08. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₈N₄O₂ : C, 71.34; H, 4.90; N, 15.13.

N'-(4-Methoxybenzylidene)-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1H-benzof[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**3b₂**) :

IR (KBr) : 3436.15, 3135.33 (N-H str.), 3044.42 (aromatic C-H str.), 2970.64, 2880.26 (C-H str.), 1667.75 (C=O str.), 1585.72 (C=N str.), 1244.27 (C-N str.); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 3.76 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.81 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 6.98–8.25 (11H, m, Ar), 8.46 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 13.09 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.45 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 423.25 (M+Na), m.p. 285–287°C. Anal. Found : C, 68.93; H, 5.00; N, 13.95. Calcd. for C₂₃H₂₀N₄O₃ : C, 68.99; H, 5.03; N, 13.99.

2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-*N'*-(4-nitrobenzylidene)-1H-benzof[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**3b₃**) :

IR (KBr) : 3434.57, 3132.89 (N-H str.), 3052.4 (aromatic C-H str.), 2970.25, 2868.46 (C-H str.), 1669.27 (C=O str.), 1586.42 (C=N str.), 1235.49 (C-N str.); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 3.85, 7.22–8.31 (11H, m, Ar), 8.51 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 13.03 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.54 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 438.24 (M+Na), m.p. 306–307°C. Anal. Found : C, 63.58; H, 4.08; N, 16.81. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₇N₅O₄ : C, 63.61; H, 4.12; N, 16.86.

2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-*N'*-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene)-1H-benzof[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**3b₄**) :

IR (KBr) : 3432.61, 3142.74 (N-H str.), 3044.31 (aromatic C-H str.), 2970.46, 2864.42 (C-H str.), 1668.41 (C=O str.), 1582.09 (C=N str.), 1244.15 (C-N str.); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 3.80 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.32–7.98 (10H, m, Ar), 8.38 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 13.04 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.50 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 400.02 (M+Na), m.p. 264–266°C. Anal. Found : C, 63.76;

H, 4.22; N, 14.84. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₆N₄O₂S : C, 63.81; H, 4.28; N, 14.88.

N'-Benzylidene-2-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-benzof[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**3c₁**) :

IR (KBr) : 3426.21, 3116.14 (N-H str.), 3043.23 (aromatic C-H str.), 2975.46, 2821.27 (C-H str.), 1660.84 (C=O str.), 1580.73 (C=N str.), 1244.81 (C-N str.); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 7.24–8.30 (12H, m, Ar), 8.49 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 13.06 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.54 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 408.28 (M+Na), m.p. 318–320°C. Anal. Found : C, 65.40; H, 3.88; N, 18.11. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₅N₅O₃ : C, 65.45; H, 3.92; N, 18.17.

N'-(4-Methoxybenzylidene)-2-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-benzof[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**3c₂**) :

IR (KBr) : 3436.16, 3128.45 (N-H str.), 3046.78 (aromatic C-H str.), 2967.27, 2895.23 (C-H str.), 1667.84 (C=O), 1581.92 (C=N str.), 1249.45 (C-N str.); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 3.84 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 7.08–8.32 (11H, m, Ar), 8.52 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 12.96 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.54 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 438.24 (M+Na), m.p. 325–327°C. Anal. Found : C, 63.56; H, 4.08; N, 16.82. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₇N₅O₄ : C, 63.61; H, 4.12; N, 16.86.

N'-(4-Nitrobenzylidene)-2-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-benzof[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**3c₃**) :

IR (KBr) : 3434.62, 3131.53 (N-H str.), 3047.83 (aromatic C-H str.), 2980.85, 2816.82 (C-H str.), 1680.48 (C=O str.), 1579.70 (C=N str.), 1244.41 (C-N str.); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 7.40–8.32 (11H, m, Ar), 8.53 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 13.05 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.59 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 453.21 (M+Na), m.p. 338–340°C. Anal. Found : C, 58.56; H, 3.22; N, 19.49. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₄N₆O₅ : C, 58.61; H, 3.28; N, 19.53.

2-(4-Nitrophenyl)-*N'*-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene)-1H-benzof[d]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**3c₄**) :

IR (KBr) : 3416.54, 3143.48 (N-H str.), 3041.23 (aromatic C-H str.), 2975.14, 2864.81 (C-H str.),

1667.83 (C=O str.), 1590.12 (C=N str.), 1245.24 (C-N str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 7.19–8.30 (10H, m, Ar), 8.41 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 12.92 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.51 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 414.15 (M+Na), m.p. 329–331°C. Anal. Found : C, 58.24; H, 3.30; N, 17.82. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_5\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 58.30; H, 3.35; N, 17.89.

N'-Benzylidene-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-1H-benzod[*j*]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**3d₁**) :

IR (KBr) : 3432.03, 3138.3 (N-H str.), 3041.93 (aromatic C-H str.), 2977.40, 2889.20 (C-H str.), 1667.61 (C=O str.), 1582.92 (C=N str.), 1249.45 (C-N str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 7.28–7.99 (11H, m, Ar), 8.44 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 13.03 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.58 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 369.16 (M+Na), m.p. 256–258°C. Anal. Found : C, 65.83; H, 4.01; N, 16.12. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$: C, 65.88; H, 4.07; N, 16.17.

N'-(4-Methoxybenzylidene)-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-1H-benzod[*j*]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**3d₂**) :

IR (KBr) : 3430.16, 3134.15 (N-H str.), 3056.58 (aromatic C-H str.), 2984.73, 2875.42 (C-H str.), 1669.76 (C=O str.), 1578.24 (C=N str.), 1244.29 (C-N str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 3.84 (1H, s, -OCH₃), 7.11–7.89 (10H, m, Ar), 8.45 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 13.01 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.54 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 399.21 (M+Na), m.p. 270–272°C. Anal. Found : C, 63.76; H, 4.25; N, 14.83. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 63.81; H, 4.28; N, 14.88.

N'-(4-Nitrobenzylidene)-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-1H-benzod[*j*]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**3d₃**) :

IR (KBr) : 3436.41, 3131.46 (N-H str.), 3049.23 (aromatic C-H str.), 2990.15, 2884.73 (C-H str.), 1672.64 (C=O str.), 1579.91 (C=N str.), 1244.85 (C-N str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 7.26–8.29 (10H, m, Ar), 8.51 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 13.03 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.57 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 414.12 (M+Na), m.p. 290–292°C. Anal. Found : C, 58.26; H, 3.30; N, 17.83. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_5\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 58.30; H, 3.35; N, 17.89.

2-(Thiophen-2-yl)-*N'*-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene)-1H-benzod[*j*]imidazole-4-carbohydrazide (**3d₄**) :

IR (KBr) : 3432.34, 3129.15 (N-H str.), 3044.43 (aromatic C-H str.), 2967.19, 2865.41 (C-H str.), 1667.16 (C=O str.), 1581.92 (C=N str.), 1253.16 (C-N str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 7.18–7.86 (9H, m, Ar), 8.38 (1H, s, =CH azomethine), 12.88 (1H, s, -NH hydrazone), 13.36 (1H, s, -NH imidazole). MS : m/z 375.13 (M+Na), m.p. 240–242°C. Anal. Found : C, 57.88; H, 3.39; N, 15.84. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{OS}_2$: C, 57.93; H, 3.43; N, 15.90.

Conclusions

We have successfully developed a simple and efficient method for synthesis of novel hydrazones Schiff bases **3a₁**–**3d₄** including with benzimidazole moiety. The characterization of the title compounds were confirmed by FT-IR, $^1\text{H NMR}$ and Mass spectra studies. All these novel compounds were evaluated for *in vitro* antimicrobial activities against four strains of bacteria's and one fungus. Some of these molecules have shown significant antimicrobial activities.

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